

**MATEMATIKA DARSLARIDA AYRIM TRIGONOMETRIK
TENGSIZLIKLARNI ISBOTLASHNING NOAN'ANAVIY
USULLARI**

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Trigonometriya, vektor, tengsizlik, tenglik, ikki vektor orasidagi burchak.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada matematika darslarida ayrim trigonometrik tengsizliklarni noan'anaviy usullar orqali isbotlash haqida mulohaza yuritilgan.

Bugungi kunda o'quvchilar matematik masalalarni isbotlashda ko'proq tengsizliklarni isbot qilishga qiynalishadi. Bunga sabab tengsizliklar uchun asosan bir qolipga tushadigan isbotlash metodlari deyarli yo'qligidadir. Biz ushbu maqolada trigonometrik tengsizliklar uchun malum bir qoidaga tushadigan bazi tengsizliklarni vektorlar yordamida isbot qilishni o'rganamiz. Xususan yordamchi vektorlar

yordamida almashtirishlar kiritgan holda tengsizliklarni soddaroq usullar bilan isbot qilish mumkinligini ko'rib chiqamiz. Bizga \bar{a} ; \bar{b} ; \bar{c} vektorlar berilgan bo'lsin :

$$1. (\bar{a}, \bar{b}) = |\bar{a}| * |\bar{b}| * \cos(\bar{a} \wedge \bar{b})$$

$$2. (\bar{a} + \bar{b}, \bar{c}) = (\bar{a}, \bar{c}) + (\bar{b}, \bar{c})$$

Endi quyidagicha shartni kiritamiz $|\bar{a}| = |\bar{b}| = |\bar{c}| = 1$

$$x + y + z = 2\pi$$

$$(\bar{a} + \bar{b} + \bar{c}, \bar{a} + \bar{b} + \bar{c}) = |\bar{a} + \bar{b} + \bar{c}|^2 \geq 0$$

$$(\bar{a} + \bar{b} + \bar{c}, \bar{a} + \bar{b} + \bar{c}) = |\bar{a}|^2 + |\bar{b}|^2 + |\bar{c}|^2 + 2|\bar{a}| * |\bar{b}| \cos z + 2|\bar{a}| * |\bar{c}| \cos y + 2|\bar{b}| * |\bar{c}| \cos x$$

Bu tengsizlikdan $\cos x + \cos y + \cos z \geq -\frac{3}{2}$, $x + y + z = 2\pi$ ga teng.

Uchburchakda esa $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = \pi$ ga teng bo'ladi. Demak quyidagi almashtirish olamiz $x = 2\alpha$, $y = 2\beta$, $z = 2\gamma$ Bu almashtirishdan

$$\cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma \geq -\frac{3}{2} \quad \text{tengsizlik}$$

hosil bo'ladi.

Endi 2α , 2β , 2γ dan qanday qilib, α , β , γ larga o'tamiz shuni ko'rib chiqamiz.

$$\cos 2\alpha = 2\cos^2 \alpha - 1, \quad \cos 2\beta = 2\cos^2 \beta - 1,$$

$$\cos 2\gamma = 2\cos^2 \gamma - 1$$

$$\cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma$$

$$= 2(\cos^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta + \cos^2 \gamma) - 3 \text{ ga teng bo'ladi.}$$

$\cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma = 2(\cos^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta + \cos^2 \gamma) - 3 \geq -\frac{3}{2}$ bundan

$\cos^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta + \cos^2 \gamma \geq \frac{3}{4}$ tengsizlik hosil bo'ladi.

$\cos^2 \alpha = 1 - \sin^2 \alpha$ $\cos^2 \beta = 1 - \sin^2 \beta$
 $\cos^2 \gamma = 1 - \sin^2 \gamma$ ifodani o'rniga qo'ysak

$\sin^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \beta + \sin^2 \gamma \leq \frac{9}{4}$ tengsizlik hosil bo'ladi. Koshi -Bunyakovskiy tengsizlikidan foydalanib yani

$$(1+1+1)(a^2+b^2+c^2) \geq (a+b+c)^2$$

$(1+1+1)(\sin^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \beta + \sin^2 \gamma) \geq (\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma)^2 \rightarrow$

$\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2}$ tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz.

Endi trigonometrik tenglikdan foydalanib quydagilarni isbot qilamiz.

$$\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma = 4 \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

$$4 \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$\cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8} \text{ bo'ladi,}$$

$\cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma = -1 - 4 \cos \alpha \cos \beta \cos \gamma$ bundan

$\cos \alpha \cos \beta \cos \gamma \leq \frac{1}{8}$ bo'ladi, bundan

$\cos \alpha + \cos \beta + \cos \gamma$ uchun tengsizlik hosil qilamiz. Buning uchun $x = \pi - \alpha$,

$y = \pi - \beta$, $z = \pi - \gamma$ deb tanlaymiz, natijada bularning yig'indisi $x + y + z = 3\pi - (\alpha + \beta + \gamma)$ ga teng bo'ladi. Bu almashtrishdan esa

quyidagi $\cos \alpha + \cos \beta + \cos \gamma \leq \frac{3}{2}$

tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz. Bundan $\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} \leq \frac{9}{4}$ bo'ladi.

Endi Koshi tengsizlikidan foydalansak

$$\frac{a+b+c}{3} \geq \sqrt[3]{abc}$$

$$\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2} \geq \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} + \cos \frac{\beta}{2} + \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \geq$$

$$3 \sqrt[3]{\cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2}} \rightarrow \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8}$$

hosil bo'ladi. Biz yuqoridagi tengsizliklarni isbotlash jarayonida quyidagi trigonometrik tengliklardan foydalandik.

$$1. \sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma = 4 \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

$$2. \cos \alpha + \cos \beta + \cos \gamma = 1 + 4 \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2} \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

$$3. \sin 2\alpha + \sin 2\beta + \sin 2\gamma = 4 \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma$$

$$4. \cos 2\alpha + \cos 2\beta + \cos 2\gamma = -1 - 4 \cos \alpha \cos \beta \cos \gamma$$

$$5. \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\beta}{2} + \operatorname{tg} \frac{\beta}{2} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\gamma}{2} + \operatorname{tg} \frac{\gamma}{2} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} = 1$$

$$6. \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\beta}{2} + \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\beta}{2} \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\gamma}{2} + \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\gamma}{2} \operatorname{ctg} \frac{\alpha}{2} = 1$$

$$7. \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} + 2 \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2} \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} = 1$$

$$8. \cos^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta + \cos^2 \gamma + 2 \cos \alpha \cos \beta \cos \gamma = 1$$

Bu tengliklarni isbotlashni o'quvchilarga mustaqil topshiriq sifatida tavsiya qilishimiz mumkin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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